

A Proposed Adaptive Nonlinear Observer Algorithm for Lithium-Ion Battery SOC and SOH Estimation for Electric Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Due to a variety of internal and external battery impacts, it is now more challenging to accurately estimate the State of Charge (SOC) and State of Health (SOH) of lithium-ion batteries used in Electric Vehicles (EVs). The paper's primary goal is to accurately predict the lithium-ion battery's SOC and SOH. The first-order RC electrical equivalent circuit model is taken into consideration for analysis and modelling in this work. In order to estimate the true parameters and internal states of the battery, the Adaptive Nonlinear Observer (ANO) is developed to transform nonlinear equations into linearized equations. The transfer function is then derived from the linearized equations. The suggested ANO provides superior dynamic results when compared to the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), and the convergence rate is examined using the linear criterion. The MATLAB/Simulink platform has been used to validate the simulation findings of the suggested ANO.

Keywords: Electric Vehicle, Adaptive Nonlinear Observer, State of Charge, State of Health.

1. Introduction:

The use of electric vehicles (EVs) in transportation networks is growing. However, because of their many benefits—such as their high energy density, high power density, high reliability, efficiency, and safe operation—lithium-ion batteries are frequently utilized in EVs (Hannan, M.A. Lipu et al, 2017). The battery is protected and monitored by the Battery Management System (BMS) from a number of abnormal circumstances, such as overcharging and elevated temperatures. For the greatest performance of EVs, the BMS's primary job is to accurately assess the battery's State of Charge and State of Health (M. S. Hossain Lipu, M. A. Hannan, Aini Hussain, 2018).

For the lithium-ion battery to operate safely, precise SOC estimation is necessary. SOC is defined as the current charge available in the battery to the battery's entire capacity (Hoque, M.M. Hannan et al, 2017). Depth of Discharge (DOD) is the inverse of SOC; picture (1) depicts the SOC comprehension diagram. There are numerous ways to obtain the state of charge (SOC) of lithium-ion batteries, but each has pros and cons, which are listed in table (1). The battery's figure of merit, or SOH, provides information about the battery's current state and usable life as compared to ideal conditions (Rajakumar Sakile, Umesh Kumar Sinha., 2020). The coulomb-counting method and open-circuit voltage methods are popularly used in the BMS for SOC estimation, these methods implementation is very easy and computation is very fast, but due to some disturbances and uncertainties these methods are not suitable for the SOC estimation and also the above said two methods are called as direct methods, suitable only for the open-loop systems (Hoque, M.M.; Hannan, M.A.; Mohamed, Ayob A, 2017). Whereas indirect methods or adaptive methods are proposed for the estimation of SOC, Kalman Filter (KF) method is also one of the famous techniques to obtain the

valid SOC, but the lithium-ion battery contains many nonlinearities (Yuan Zou, Xiaosong Hu, et al, 2017). Formerly KF method is applicable only for linear systems and it requires more time for gain calculations, calculation time is more than the sampling time and thus it was unable to track the correct state value. Modified KF methods are also introduced to obtain the accurate SOC those are Extended Kalman Filter and Unscented Kalman Filter methods (Wuzhao Yan, Bin Zhang et al, 2018).

Figure1. SOC understand diagram

Other methods are reported for the estimation of correct SOC as artificial neural network and fuzzy logic systems. The neural network method is not suitable for online implementation due to a large imbalance in the system. Fuzzy logic methods are depending on the training data and require a complex controller.

Table1. Advantages and Disadvantages of SOC estimation methods

S. No	Name of the method	Advantages	Disadvantages
1	Coulomb counting method (Xiaopeng Tang, Yujie wang et al, 2015)	Simple, easy implementation and fast computation	Applicable only for open- loop systems and this method is very sensitive
2	Open circuit voltage method (Changfu Zou, Chris Manzie et al, 2016)	Simple, easy implementation	Applicable only for open-loop systems and unsuitable for flat OCV-SOC curves
3	Kalman filter-based method (Zhang, Z.L. Cheng et al, 2017)	Accurate and commonly used method in literature, closed-loop system	Improved methods only suitable for the nonlinear systems and complexity
4	Neural network method (Bizhong Xia, Zizhou Lao, Ruifeng Zhang 2018))	More accurate	Sensitive to the training data and the complex controller is required
5	Fuzzy logic method (Hannan, M.A. Lipu et al, 2017)	More accurate, robust	Sensitive to the training data and the complex controller is required
6	Least squares method (Duong, V.H. Bastawrous et al, 2015)	Accurate, robust	Higher computational cost
7	Proposed method (Adaptive Nonlinear Observer)	Precise, robust, simple structure, closed-loop	Computational cost is higher than filters.

		system and applicable for nonlinear systems.
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In this paper, An Adaptive Nonlinear Observer (ANO) is proposed for the estimation of SOC and SOH of the lithium-ion battery. The ANO overcomes the drawbacks of existing systems and makes it easier for the control structure. The paper was organised into 5 sections, section-1 deals with the introduction, sections-2 explained the design of ANO, section-3 overview the battery modelling, section-4 & 5 explained the simulation results and conclusion respectively.

2. Design of Adaptive Nonlinear Observer:

An observer is a system it will provide information about the internal states of the given real system. Practically, the physical states of any system cannot be determined directly. Therefore, indirect observers are required to estimate the accurate internal states of the system. Sliding mode and extended observers are commonly used for nonlinear systems (Mehdi Gholizadeh, Alireza Yazdzizadeh, 2020, Yong tian, Chaoren Chen ,2014). A sliding mode observer (SMO) is used to estimate the SOC of lithium-ion battery pack, but it is not suitable for the estimation of SOC (Sarah K. Spurgeon ,2008). SMO leading to the large model error due to the highly nonlinear relationship between SOC and OCV. Lemberger observer is also one of the important observers to estimate the SOC of the battery, unfortunately, it was increasing the complexity to determine the Jacobian matrix. To avoid the above-said problems, Adaptive Nonlinear Observer (ANO) is proposed for the estimation of the SOC. The proposed ANO discussed as follows (Wuzhao Yan, Bin Zhang et al, 2018).

ANO is designed for the estimation of states and circuit parameters of the system.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \psi(t) &= A(\psi(t), x(t), \delta(t)) \\ y(t) &= B(\psi(t), \delta(t)) \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where A,B are the two nonlinear functions, $x(t)$, $y(t)$ and $\psi(t)$ represents the input , output and state vectors respectively (Pascal Messier, Bao-Huy Nguyen et al, 2020). $\delta(t)$ represents the unknown vector parameter and it was assumed that $\delta(t) \neq 0$ (Due to satisfy the system observability the unknown parameter vector considered to be zero). Define $\phi = [\psi \quad \delta]^T$, an augmented equations are as follows.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \phi &= A(y, x) \\ y &= B(y) \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

To linearizing the above augmented equations, an operating point (ϕ_0, x_0) consequence in

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta\phi^{\square} &= F.\Delta\phi + G.\Delta x \\ \Delta y &= H.\Delta\phi \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where, $\Delta x = x - x_0$, $\Delta\phi = \phi - \phi_0$, $\Delta y = y - y_0$ and from equation (3), F,G and H obtained as

$$F = \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial \phi} \right|_{(\phi_0, x_0)}; G = \left. \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \right|_{(\phi_0, x_0)}; H = \left. \frac{\partial y}{\partial \phi} \right|_{(\phi_0, x_0)} \dots\dots (4)$$

In order to maintain the linearly observable, the observer from equation (2) is given by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \phi^{\wedge \square} &= A(\phi^{\wedge}, x) + L(y - B(\phi^{\wedge})) \\ y^{\wedge \square} &= B(\phi) \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

To linearize the above observer, the operating point approximately to the $(\phi_0^{\wedge}, x_0) \overset{\Delta}{\approx} (\phi_0, x_0)$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta\phi^{\wedge \square} &= C.\Delta\phi^{\wedge} + D.\Delta x + Z(\Delta y - \Delta y^{\wedge}) \\ \Delta y^{\wedge \square} &= E.\Delta\phi^{\wedge} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Δ is removed for simplicity notation, from the equation (3) above equation (6) can be written as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \phi^{\wedge \square} &= C\phi^{\wedge} + Dx + Z(\phi - \phi^{\wedge}) \\ y^{\wedge \square} &= E\phi^{\wedge} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Consider $\phi = [\psi \ \delta]^T$, system equation (3) is decomposed as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \phi^{\square} \\ \delta^{\square} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ \delta \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} D_1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} x \\ y &= \begin{bmatrix} E_1 & E_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ \delta \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Consider the feedback Gain $Z = [Z_1 \ Z_2]^T$ and the equation (8) can be modified as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \phi^{\wedge \square} \\ \delta^{\wedge \square} \end{bmatrix} = \left(\begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi^{\wedge} \\ \delta^{\wedge} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} D_1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} x + \begin{bmatrix} Z_1 \\ Z_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E_1 & E_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi - \phi^{\wedge} \\ \delta - \delta^{\wedge} \end{bmatrix} \right) \dots\dots (9)$$

From equation (8) and (9)

$$\phi^{\square} = C_{11} \phi + C_{12} \delta + D_1 x \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

$$\delta^{\square} = 0$$

$$\phi^{\square} = C_{11} \phi^{\wedge} + C_{12} \delta^{\wedge} + D_1 x + Z_1 E_1 (\phi - \phi^{\wedge}) + Z_2 E_2 (\delta - \delta^{\wedge}) \quad \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

$$\delta^{\square} = Z_2 E_1 (\phi - \phi^{\wedge}) + Z_2 E_2 (\delta - \delta^{\wedge}) \quad \dots\dots\dots (12)$$

From (10) and (11)

$$\phi - \phi^{\square} = (C_{11} - Z_1 E_1) (\phi - \phi^{\wedge}) + (C_{12} - Z_1 E_2) (\delta - \delta^{\wedge}) \quad \dots\dots\dots (13)$$

Apply Laplace transform on both sides to the equation (13)

$$s \phi(s) - \phi^{\wedge}(s) = s (C_{11} - Z_1 E_1) (\phi(s) - \phi^{\wedge}(s)) + s (C_{12} - Z_1 E_2) (\delta(s) - \delta^{\wedge}(s))$$

After rewrite the above equation, the modified equation obtained as

$$(J_{\phi} - C_{11} + Z_1 E_1) (\phi(s) - \phi^{\wedge}(s)) = (C_{12} - Z_1 E_2) (\delta(s) - \delta^{\wedge}(s)) \quad \dots\dots (14)$$

J_{ϕ} represented as identity matrix for ϕ dimension, apply the Laplace transform to the equation (12) and by using the equation (14) the obtained one as,

$$\delta^{\wedge}(s) = Z_2 E_1 (s\phi(s) - s\phi^{\wedge}(s)) + Z_2 E_2 (s\delta(s) - s\delta^{\wedge}(s)) \quad \dots\dots\dots (15)$$

$$\delta^{\wedge}(s) = \left[sJ_p + Z_2 E_1 (sJ_{\phi} - C_{11} + Z_1 E_1)^{-1} (C_{12} - Z_1 E_2) + Z_2 E_2 \right]^{-1} * \dots\dots\dots (16)$$

$$\left[Z_2 E_1 (sJ_{\phi} - C_{11} + Z_1 E_1)^{-1} (C_{12} - Z_1 E_2) + Z_2 E_2 \right] \delta(s)$$

The above equation (16) can be known as transfer function form of $\delta^{\wedge}(s)$ and $\delta(s)$, the same equation can be modified as

$$\delta^{\wedge}(s) = \Gamma(s) \delta(s) \quad \dots\dots\dots (17)$$

Apply the final value theorem to the above equation in Laplace s domain

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s. \delta^{\wedge}(s) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s. \Gamma(s) \delta(s) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \Gamma(s) * \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s. \delta(s) = 0$$

From the final value theorem, it is noticed that all the poles are laying on left -half of the s-plane and (C, E) is assumed to be linearly observable. Therefore, the internal states of any system can be determined easily (Xiaopeng Tang, Yujie wang et al, 2018). Since the parameter estimation is its real value. The observer gain of the system $Z = [Z_1 \ Z_2]^T$ is determined by the pole placement method or Hurwitz method based on the high convergence rate (Mehdi Gholizadeh, Alireza Yazdizadeh, 2020).

3. Battery Modelling:

To determine the SOC and SOH of lithium-ion battery it is required to develop a battery model. To validate the presented observer, battery modelling is required. The battery model is also known as an electrical equivalent circuit model, it consists of the nonlinear voltage source ($U_{oc}(SOC)$), Internal

resistance (R_{int}) and polarized resistance and capacitance (Rajakumar Sakile, Umesh Kumar Sinha, 2020, Li Sun, Guanru Li, Fengqi You et al, 2020). The battery equivalent circuit is shown in fig (2), this circuit involves many nonlinear elements i.e. Voltage source representing the nonlinear relationship between Open circuit voltage and SOC of the battery. SOC of the battery model expressed as,

$$x(t) = x_0(t) - \frac{1}{Q} \int \eta * I_L(t) dt \dots\dots\dots (18)$$

Where $x(t)$ represents the SOC of the lithium-ion battery, $x_0(t)$ is called as initial SOC of the battery, Q considered as rated capacity of the battery, η represented as coulombic efficiency of the battery usually it should be treated as one and I_L represented as load current of the battery (Qiaoyan Chen, Jiuchun Jiang, 2017).

Figure2. Battery equivalent circuit model

Derive the equation (18) with respect to time, then the equation (18) can be obtained as,

$$\dot{x}(t) = -\frac{1}{Q} * I_L - a_1 I_L \dots\dots\dots (19)$$

From the battery equivalent circuit, the derived equations as follows

$$-U_{oc}(SOC) - I_L R_{int} + V_p + U_t = 0$$

$$U_t = U_{oc}(SOC) - I_L R_{int} - V_p \dots\dots\dots (20)$$

$$V_p = \frac{-V_p}{R_p \cdot C_p} + \frac{I_L}{C_p} \cong -b_1 V_p + b_2 I_L \dots\dots (21)$$

Describing the nonlinear function $U_{oc}(SOC)$

$$U_{oc}(SOC) \cong k(SOC) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SOC + \beta_2 SOC^2 + \beta_3 SOC^3 + \beta_4 SOC^4 + \beta_5 SOC^5 + \beta_6 SOC^6 \dots\dots (22)$$

From the equation (20), the load current expressed as,

$$U_t + V_p - U_{oc}(SOC) = I_L R_{int}$$

$$I_L = \frac{1}{R_{int}} [k(SOC) - U_t - V_p]$$

Substitute the load current expression in the equation (19)

$$\dot{x}(t) = \left[\frac{-1}{R_{int} C_p} (k(SOC) - U_t - V_p) \right] \dots\dots\dots (26)$$

Derive the equation (20) with respect to time

$$\dot{U}_t = SOC * \dot{U}_{oc}(SOC) - \dot{V}_p \dots\dots\dots (27)$$

$$\dot{U}_{oc}(SOC) = \frac{\partial k(SOC)}{\partial SOC}$$

$$= \beta_1 + 2\beta_2 SOC + 3\beta_3 SOC^2 + 4\beta_4 SOC^3 + 5\beta_5 SOC^4 + 6\beta_6 SOC^5$$

From equation (21), (26) and (27)

$$\dot{U}_t = b_2 \dot{V}_p - [a_1 * U_{oc}(SOC) + a_2] I_L \dots\dots (28)$$

From equation (20)

$$V_p = k(SOC) - U_t - I_L R_{int}, \text{ Substitute } V_p \text{ in the equation (28)}$$

$$\dot{U}_t = b_2 (k(SOC) - U_t - I_L R_{int}) - [a_1 * U_{oc}(SOC) + a_2] I_L \dots\dots\dots (29)$$

Consider $x(t)$, $y(t)$ and $\psi(t)$ represents the input, output and state vectors respectively, $x = I_L$, $y = U_t$

and $\psi = [U_t \quad SOC \quad V_p]^T$.

The proposed ANO estimates the accurate SOC and SOH of the lithium-ion battery, the internal resistance of the battery is estimated as an unknown parameter i.e. $\delta = R_{int}$ and changes occur in the parameter indicated as SOH of the battery. The battery model equations are completely nonlinear equation's and there is no possibility to check whether the system is observable or not, then the ANO is proposed to convert nonlinear equation's into linearized equations. By using the converted linear equations, conduct the observability test to check the obtained linear equations are observable or not. If the system is completely observable, then the internal states of any system can be obtained easily.

$$\dot{\psi} = \begin{bmatrix} b_2 k(\psi_2) - b_2 \psi_1 \\ \frac{-a_1}{R_{int}} k(\psi_2) - \psi_1 - \psi_3 \\ -b_2 \psi_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -a_1 U_{oc} \psi_2 - a_2 - R_{int} b_2 \\ 0 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} x \dots\dots\dots (30)$$

$$y = \psi_1$$

Consider the equation $\delta^{\square} = R_{int} = 0$, $\phi = [\psi \ \delta]^T = [U_t \ \text{SOC} \ V_p \ R_{int}]^T$. Linearizing the above system for (ϕ_0, x_0) , the system matrices are determined as,

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -b_2 & b_2 U_{oc}(\phi_2) - a_1 x_0 U_{oc}^{\square}(\phi_2) & 0 \\ \frac{a_1}{\phi_4} & \frac{-a_1}{\phi_4} U_{oc}(\phi_2) & \frac{a_1}{\phi_4} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} -b_2 x_0 \\ \frac{-a_1}{\phi_4^2} (k(\phi_2) - \phi_1 - \phi_3) \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; E = \begin{bmatrix} [1 \ 0 \ 0] & [0] \end{bmatrix} = [E_1 \ E_2] \dots\dots\dots (31)$$

The observability matrix for linearized system is given by $\theta_0 = [E \ EC \ EC^2 \ EC^3]^T$, By doing mathematical calculations, θ_0 is full row rank therefore, (E, C) are completely observable. Thus, the proposed ANO has the capability to estimate the unknown parameters and internal states of the system.

4. Simulation Results and Discussion:

Consider the lithium-ion battery capacity as 2500mAh and the nominal voltage of the battery is 3.7V. The OCV-SOC fitting curve was described from equation (22) as shown in figure (2), the coefficients of the equation (22) are as follows.

$$\beta_0 = 3.61; \beta_1 = 2.032; \beta_2 = -4.052; \beta_3 = -5.237; \beta_4 = 31.61; \beta_5 = -36.62; \beta_6 = 14.22;$$

Figure (3) shows the battery terminal voltage and current, derived equation (30) is considered as input and output of the battery model. To estimate SOC and SOH, battery voltage and current treated as input signal of the proposed ANO. Substitute all the true values in the equation (31) and get the linearized system matrices.

$$C_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0403 & 0.0110 & 0 \\ 0.0056 & -0.0021 & 0.0056 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.403 \end{bmatrix}; C_{12} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.02 \\ -0.031 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \dots\dots\dots (32)$$

The observer gain matrix is given by $Z = [[Z_{11} \ Z_{12} \ Z_{13}] [Z_2]]^T$

The transfer function from δ to δ^{\wedge} is given by

$$\Gamma(s) = \frac{Z_2 E_1 (sJ_p - C_{11} + Z_1 E_1) (C_{12} - Z_1 E_2) + Z_2 E_2}{s + (sJ_\phi - C_{11} + Z_1 E_1) (C_{12} - Z_1 E_2) + Z_2 E_2} \dots\dots\dots (33)$$

According to the equation (32)

$$Z_2 E_2 = 0; \quad C_{11} - Z_1 E_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0403 - Z_{11} & 0.0110 & 0 \\ 0.0056 - Z_{12} & -0.0021 & 0.0056 \\ -Z_{13} & 0 & -0.403 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_{12} - Z_1 E_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.02 \\ -0.031 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad Z_2 E_1 = [Z_2 \quad 0 \quad 0]$$

After solving equation (33), the poles of the transfer function of $\Gamma(s)$ is -0.02, -0.02, -0.05, -0.05, the obtained gain of the proposed ANO is as

$$Z = [0.0689 \quad 0.192 \quad -0.192 \quad -0.04]^T$$

From equation (30) the modified equation obtained as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \psi^{\wedge} \\ R^{\wedge}_{int} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_2 k(\psi_2^{\wedge}) - b_2 \psi_1^{\wedge} - (a_1 U_{oc}(\psi_2^{\wedge}) + a_2 + R^{\wedge}_{int} b_2) x \\ \frac{-a_1}{R^{\wedge}_{int}} (k(\psi_2^{\wedge}) - \psi_1^{\wedge} - \psi_3^{\wedge}) \\ -b_2 \psi_3^{\wedge} + a_2 x \end{bmatrix} + Z (\psi_1 - \psi_1^{\wedge})$$

$$y = \psi_1^{\wedge}$$

To know the performance of the ANO, it is compared with one of the most recognized methods and frequently used algorithm named Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) in terms of accuracy and convergence rate. The reason behind the comparison with the EKF method is, it was established as a better method for the estimation of accurate SOC of lithium-ion battery. The detailed literature survey of the EKF algorithm originates in the references (Zhang, Z.L, Cheng et, al, 2017, Bizhong Xia, Zizhou Lao et, al, 2018). Figure (5) and (6) shows that the comparison of accurate SOC value at SOC=1 (100%) and SOC=0.5 (50%), After comparison, the proposed ANO gives better dynamic results compared to the EKF method. EKF method is not suitable for highly nonlinear systems, whereas the proposed ANO well suitable for the highly nonlinear characteristics and gives well-established results.

Figure3. OCV-SOC curve of a lithium-ion battery

Figure 4: Battery voltage and current profile

Figure 5: Difference between proposed ANO method and true SOC with at SOC=1

Figure 6: Difference between proposed ANO method and true SOC with at SOC=0.5

Figure 7: Relation between SOC and internal resistance

To know the effectiveness of the Proposed ANO, two comparison waveforms are generated as shown in figure (5) and (6) at different SOC conditions like SOC=1 and SOC=0.5. The two waveforms are compared with the well-designed EKF method, the proposed ANO follows the true SOC as shown in figure (5), therefore, Proposed ANO has been improved the estimation accuracy as compared to the EKF method, the same approach has been followed for the next case at SOC=0.5. Figure (7) shows the indication of SOH, the measured internal resistance itself considered as SOH of the battery, the proposed ANO designed and validated through MATLAB/Simulink platform. Finally, the proposed ANO is capable to determine accurate SOC and SOH from the nonlinear lithium-ion battery.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an ANO has been proposed for the estimation of SOC and SOH of lithium-ion battery in EVs, the first-order RC equivalent circuit model is considered to simulate the dynamic behaviour of the lithium-ion battery, the state equations are derived for the design of the proposed ANO. The proposed ANO obtained the lithium-ion battery internal resistance, which can be considered for the SOH indication of the battery. The proposed ANO has been reduced the complexity and improve the estimation of accurate SOC as compared to the EKF method and feedback gain of the ANO is obtained with the transfer function approach. Therefore, the proposed ANO is suitable for the estimation of accurate SOC with higher nonlinearities, the convergence rate of the ANO is provided by linear criterion.

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